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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

In 2015, all member states of the United Nations, including Canada, agreed to the Agenda for Sustainable Development 2030 which aims to make the world a better place through 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Astronomers are in an irreplaceable position to help Canadians reach these objectives, not only in the many choices they can make in their day-to-day teaching and research activities but also through their unique vision of the world and its inhabitants. In this white paper, we expand on these ideas and provide considerations on how the astronomical society can help Canada do its part to reach the SDGs through education and research.

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1 Introduction

In 2015, Canada, along with all United Nations Member States, adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (<https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdgs>). This ambitious agenda focuses on five “Ps”: People, Planet, Prosperity, Peace and Partnership, and is underpinned by other international normative instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. At the heart of the 2030 Agenda are 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which cover many different aspects to create a better future for all human beings but also better conditions for the planet and its ecosystems.

Astronomers are in a unique position to help Canadians reach these objectives, not only in the many choices we make in our day-to-day teaching and research activities but also through our unique vision of the world and its inhabitants. As concerned citizens, the authors feel compelled to act as we see the growing need to limit the negative impacts of human activity on our planet as well as to foster an attitude that values different opinions and diverse cultures around the world.

How can we, astronomers, make our contribution to the goal of creating a better future for all?

2 What are the Sustainable Development Goals?

The 17 United Nations 2030 SDGs are interlinked, integrated, and each SDG is accompanied by targets and indicators. They build on the decades of work by the UN and its agencies to build global partnerships for sustainable development to improve human lives and protect the environment. Together, the SDGs aim to end poverty, promote economic growth, tackle climate change and conserve ecosystems, amongst other challenges, by the year 2030, ensuring that no-one is left behind. Each UN Member State is called upon to make the 2030 Agenda a reality by educating and engaging all stakeholders to implement the global goals.

Canada submitted its first Voluntary National Review in 2018, a report highlighting national actions, achievements, challenges and next steps. Following that, Canada's federal government established an SDG unit, a funding program, and created “Towards Canada's 2030 Agenda National Strategy”, an interim strategy document. Most recently, the Minister of Environment and Climate Change produced “2019-2022 Federal Sustainable Development Strategy” setting out the Government of Canada's environmental sustainability priorities, goals, targets and actions.

The achievement of many SDGs heavily depends on science and there is not a single SDG that does not require input from STEM fields. For example, SDG4 (Quality Education) aims to promote science literacy, access and diversity, and SDG7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) has targets related to technological innovation. Overall, the SDGs recognize science as a universal public good that helps in laying the foundation for a sustainable world. They acknowledge fundamental science as a principal requirement for innovation and provide a productive scientific environment. Moreover, they emphasize that diversity in science is essential for sustainable development and identify the need to strengthen science education to increase science literacy and capacity-building in science at

all levels. This requires raising investments in science and promoting an integrated scientific approach addressing the social, economic and environmental dimensions of sustainable development and respecting the diversity of knowledge systems.

3 Why is Astronomy in a Unique Position?

We argue that astronomers are in a unique position to help Canadians reach the SDGs, because of our unique vision of the Earth and its inhabitants, of our capacity to inspire a lot of people through outreach but also because of our great ability to tackle complex problems in big, international teams.

3.1 Earth From Space

Astronomy allows us to look very far away but it also gives us a different perspective on our planet. Seeing the Earth as a small, blue ball lost in the blackness of space forces us to reconsider how we view our planet. While it looks very big on a human scale, the Earth looks extremely small in the Universe and the finite aspects of its resources become evident.

The global perspective became evident with the first pictures of Earth from space. In 1968, the Apollo 8 crew captured a beautiful shot of the Earth rising over the lunar landscape. Then in 1972, the famous Blue Marble picture taken during the Apollo 17 mission quickly became a symbol of the beauty and fragility of our planet and was linked to a boost in the environmental awareness.

From left to right: Earthrise (Apollo 8), Blue Marble (Apollo 17), Pale Blue Dot (Voyager 1)

In 1990, the Voyager spacecraft captured another amazing view of our planet. Following an idea proposed by astronomer and educator Carl Sagan, the spacecraft was ordered to turn around and take a portrait of the Solar system from a distance of 40 astronomical units. In this case, the Earth appears as a single blue pixel lost in the vastness of space. While not as aesthetically pleasing as the Blue Marble, the Pale Blue Dot had an incredible impact, thanks to the thought-provoking accompanying text written by Carl Sagan in 1994:

We succeeded in taking that picture [from deep space], and, if you look at it, you see a dot. That's here. That's home. That's us. On it, everyone you ever heard of, every human being who ever lived, lived out their lives. The aggregate of all our joys and sufferings, thousands of confident religions, ideologies and economic doctrines, every hunter and forager, every hero and coward, every creator and destroyer of civilizations, every king and peasant, every young couple in love, every hopeful child, every mother and father, every inventor and explorer, every teacher of morals, every corrupt politician, every superstar, every supreme leader, every saint and sinner in the history of our species, lived there on a mote of dust, suspended in a sunbeam. (...) To my mind, there is perhaps no better demonstration of the folly of human conceits than this distant image of our tiny world. To me, it underscores our responsibility to deal more kindly and compassionately with one another and to preserve and cherish that pale blue dot, the only home we've ever known.

This vision of the Earth as a small, unique planet, is enhanced by the various research projects conducted by astronomers and other scientists to better understand the past and current evolution of the planet itself, the planets and satellites of the Solar system, and more recently, the exoplanets. More than ever, astronomers are in a unique position to appreciate how the Earth and its life forms - including humans - evolved together in an extremely well balanced environment. The conditions on Earth might not be unique, but research tells us they are extremely rare and fine-tuned.

3.2 Inspiration through Education and Outreach

Astronomy is inspiring and can connect with people in ways few other scientific topics can. The beauty and mysteries of the cosmos. Seeing thousands of stars in the night sky. Realizing our place in the Universe. These are all ways astronomy can reach people and make them experience something different than their everyday life. We believe this is an important strength of our field.

Many astronomers across Canada are very active in education and public outreach activities and the many requests from media, schools, libraries are rarely all met. This is an amazing opportunity to interact with an increasing number of people every year, especially since scientists are considered by the public as being people they can trust, and astronomers are in general highly regarded by the public. We think astronomers should consider embracing this role of agent of positive change in their education and public outreach activities and use it to inspire people to do better.

3.3 Unique Qualities and Experiences

Beyond the field of astronomy itself, the people doing astronomy research have skills which can help reach the SDGs.

Sciences such as physics and astronomy have led the way to many technologies and to an expertise being used today to study our planet. Constant monitoring of the Earth is now possible thanks to satellites working at different wavelengths. Furthermore, astronomers bring an interesting perspective to that data by studying other objects in the Solar system and beyond. Understanding the characteristics of the Earth in relation to other planets puts astronomers in a better position to put this information in context.

Moreover, because of their universal research objectives, astronomers coming from all over the world have been working together for centuries. This experience of working hand in hand to reach ambitious goals has made astronomers great leaders to promote the concept of global citizenship. Astronomers are recognized for their strong ability to think differently and to create innovative solutions to complex problems, working in teams that are increasingly diverse. These skills could be put into profit when finding ways to create new research projects which align with the SDGs.

Those strengths are more important than ever to address the challenges associated with climate change and a global interconnected world.

4 How can Astronomers Contribute?

While we can find links between astronomy and the 17 SDGs, their targets and indicators, we prefer to make a more global approach to how astronomers can contribute. Our field encompasses the whole planet and can have an impact anywhere in all 17 SDGs. We encourage everyone to have a look at the SDGs as well as their targets and indicators and think of ways they can contribute. Many teams around the world are already working on this subject (Willebrands & Russo; Office of Astronomy for Development...) and we are inspired by their work. Here, we have decided to separate the contribution of astronomy in two main parts: education and research activities.

4.1 Education

Through their educational and outreach activities, astronomers can help the public of all ages get a global perspective on the Earth. We strongly urge the astronomy community to become aware of the potential of their field to make people think about their place in the Universe and the unique conditions of our planet. We believe education about astronomy should inspire everyone to view the Earth and its inhabitants differently.

4.1.1 Global Citizenship

The idea of global citizenship, that all humans are equal regardless of their origin on the planet, becomes obvious as we look at Earth from space. From an astronomical perspective, we're all citizens of Earth before being citizens of different countries. This way of looking at our world can have profound impacts on how we see all human beings, and all life forms on Earth. Understanding the global perspective can help humans have more empathy towards one another. This in turn can lead to better conditions for everyone.

WE ARE ALL CITIZENS OF PLANET EARTH

We believe this way of looking at our planet can greatly improve relationships in the world. As we see the importance of collaboration between people of different backgrounds, values and cultures, we strongly believe the global perspective could help humans cooperate better with each other.

Any SDG that deals with improving the conditions of all human beings can link back to the concept of Global Citizenship:

The concept of global citizenship is itself included in target 4.3 in the SDG 4 - Quality Education as a way to promote sustainable development in education.

4.1.2 Earth as a Finite Resource

Seeing the Earth from space also gives us a different perspective on its resources. The Earth is a finite place which cannot sustain infinite growth. Both our population and our technological impact have grown drastically in the last century. This now puts a stress on our resources which cannot last forever.

THE EARTH IS THE ONLY HOME WE HAVE

When seeing the Earth as a finite planet, we quickly realize that the amount of water, especially freshwater, is limited and has been recycled for millennia. The atmosphere also seems incredibly tenuous when viewed as a thin layer surrounding our planet. Creating models with the right amount of water or thickness of the atmosphere can send very powerful messages.

SDG 13 - Climate Action is one SDG where astronomers can concretely help with their expertise. Astronomers have knowledge that can help the general public understand the reasons for climate change and they should take every opportunity they have to educate everyone.

Any SDG linked to the resources of the Earth and the interconnections of all life forms can be included in the category of Earth as a Finite Resource.

In the last half-century, we have seen many astronomers dedicating their time to defend equality of chances and the environment. Carl Sagan is probably the most famous example but we can also think of Hubert Reeves, French-Canadian astrophysicist, and more recently Aurélien Barrau, from France, who have become strong advocates for environmental causes. Without necessarily playing such a large role in the public sphere, we think every Canadian astrophysicist could exploit the many tribunes they have in to share their knowledge to help the public become aware of the importance and fragility of our planet and how we are all interconnected.

We strongly recommend that all astronomers consider how they can include ideas of global citizenship and the Earth as a finite resource (including climate change) in their education and outreach activities to help the public get a global perspective on our planet and its inhabitants and inspire them to act on it.

4.2 Research Activities and Infrastructure

In their research projects and in their day-to-day research activities, astronomers can make a difference by making choices that align with a more peaceful and prosperous future for all people and the planet.

4.2.1 People

In the astronomical community, we have seen the beginning of initiatives that promote inclusiveness : equity and diversity committees were created all across Canada to improve accessibility to conferences and to make the profession more inclusive so that it benefits from the competencies and strengths of people of all genders and origins. New projects should be done in partnership with local communities and integrate aspects of quality education, training of qualified personnel and job creation. We are already seeing examples in different parts of the world where astronomy is a local catalyst for positive development (ex: SKA in Africa).

4.2.2 Planet

Astronomers, with their study of the Earth, the other bodies of the Solar system and of planets in other stellar systems, have helped humans to understand our planet for decades. For example, the understanding of the runaway greenhouse effect that Venus experience or modelling of exoplanets that are similar in size and mass to Earth have made us very aware of the fragile equilibrium of planet Earth. These research projects will continue to help us understand our planet and need to be shared widely with the general population.

Astronomers as a community also need to start addressing issues related to climate change (see white paper by Matzner et al. as well as the US white paper by Williamson et al.). Already, astronomers are more and more aware of their huge personal carbon footprint. The international nature of large projects associated with astronomy and the

need for exchanges between astronomers from all over the world has made air travel ubiquitous in the community, but we have seen the beginning of initiatives that limit the systematic access to it. Astronomers can also have a positive impact by reaching ambitious environmental targets when building new observatories and research centres.

We therefore recommend that all astronomers consider the environmental and cultural impact of their current scientific activities and of any new research project and infrastructure and think of ways for these projects to fit within the guidelines of the SDGs.

5 Conclusion

In summary, astronomers have the potential to play a decisive role to ensure a peaceful future on a healthy planet Earth, in agreement with the sustainable development goals of the United Nations. Already, many astronomers have used their knowledge and resources to help Canadians understand the uniqueness of our planet, and how humans are all citizens of planet Earth. We hope this white paper will inspire more astronomers to have these objectives in mind in their research and educational activities, in the decisions they take on a day-to-day basis, and in the planning of future major infrastructure. The authors will continue working on the subject by creating educational resources, finding deeper links with individual SDGs and collaborating with teams around the world who work on the same subject. We encourage everyone interested to work on this topic to get in touch with us.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

N/A

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

N/A

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

There are already a few teams around the world working on astronomy and the Sustainable Development Goals. However, our understanding is that most projects so far have been limited in scope or are still in the early stages. Canada could definitely contribute to this endeavour and even take a leadership role, especially in terms of education.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

The Canadian Commission for UNESCO has shown an interest in our project and we will be sharing this white paper with other collaborators around the world. We hope this is the starting point of a larger collaboration.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

N/A

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

N/A

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

N/A

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

Aside from offering a better future for everyone, our initiative can lead to new EPO opportunities, great multidisciplinary projects to limit negative environmental impacts of astronomy research projects and eventually to new positions for astronomers interested in sustainable development.

6 Resources

- United Nations - Sustainable Development Goals: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdgs>
- Agenda 2030 Canada: <https://canada2030agenda.ca/>
- International Astronomical Union Strategic Plan 2020-2030: https://www.iau.org/administration/about/strategic_plan/
- Office for Astronomy for Development - OAD Projects and their link to SDGs: <http://www.astro4dev.org/blog/2018/04/24/projects-and-their-link-to-sdgs/>
- Willebrands & Russo, Astronomy & SDGs, in preparation